

STORIES OF TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' UTILIZATION OF LEARNING MATERIALS DURING BLENDED LEARNING

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 9

Pages: 1121-1135

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1918

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11663078

Manuscript Accepted: 05-10-2024

Stories of Technology and Livelihood Pre-Service Teachers' Utilization of Learning Materials During Blended Learning

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Abstract

Teaching and learning materials are resources used by educators to facilitate learning in different educational environments. This study aimed to investigate the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) pre-service teachers' utilization of learning materials during the blended learning modality. Specifically, it explored their experiences which focused on the context, challenges and coping strategies. It employed qualitative research design, specifically a narrative inquiry design that sought to figure out their experiences. The data were collected through Focus Group Discussion (FGD) from 5 BTLE pre-service teachers in a private school in Cagayan de Oro City in the school year 2022-2023 and analyzed through Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic method. Findings revealed that the contexts of their lived experiences of utilization of learning materials in blended learning revealed themes namely: academic resourcefulness, and technology literacy. Moreover, their challenges encountered include ineffective video presentation, inadequate learning materials and lack of availability of learning materials. However, it was revealed that they cope with those challenges through employing teaching strategies, embracing flexibility, demonstrating passion for teaching, relying on support systems, practicing self-discipline, and effective time management. These findings highlight the importance of equipping pre-service teachers with the necessary skills and resources to navigate blended learning environments successfully.

Keywords: *learning materials, blended learning, technology and livelihood education*

Introduction

Teaching learning materials are the gathered materials that teachers used in teaching and learning circumstances to assist the goals of learning objectives. They are tools utilized in teaching and assessment, as well as any tools and techniques a teacher use to carry out instructions and ensure students achieve their learning goals. To make learning more interesting, motivating, and engaging, they help students flesh out their experiences. Edu (2022) claimed that there are different kinds of teaching and learning materials, including language laboratories, audio and visual aids, visual aids, and computer-assisted learning. The transfer of knowledge from teacher to student is referred to as the learning process. In educational contexts, teaching and learning are facilitated by the tools and resources referred to as teaching and learning materials.

Toyosi (2018) stated that the lack of learning materials hinders effective teaching and learning. In this 21st century, students are focused in social media and dislike things that make them uncomfortable and stressed. As a result, many students do not like to listen to their teachers' discussion. Using instructional materials in the classroom helps the teacher explain new concepts clearly, leading to better student understanding of the concepts being taught. This suggests that teachers should be trained in how to use teaching materials effectively and all secondary schools should check that appropriate teaching materials are available for use in the classroom.

Moreover, Uzuegbu et al. (2013) postulate that new media resources like ICT and computer programs, the instructional materials available to university lecturers that teach library science education are insufficient to achieve the objective of effective teaching and learning. It follows that teachers', students', and parents' anxiety over their children's test results and overall learning may worsen rather than improve.

The researchers found an apparent knowledge gap in the preceding study. The foregoing study of Uzuegbu et al. (2013) primarily attempts to understand the available instructional materials to lecturers and their effective use in teaching library education in tertiary institutions. Hence, the aforementioned study failed to thoroughly study the phenomenon of pre-service teachers' utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning such as the experience and context of the mentioned phenomenon.

In the new normal, there are various studies conducted on the teachers' experiences on blending learning, however, on utilization of learning materials during blended learning is limited. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the phenomenon of TLE pre-service teachers' utilization of learning materials in blended learning. Specifically, it intended to explore the experiences, context, challenges and coping mechanisms of the pre-service teachers in teaching TLE students in blended learning.

This study assumed that learning materials assist the pre-service teachers in teaching TLE during blended learning, where they utilize different learning materials to convey their lessons in the class. This assumption is supported by Bruner's Constructivist Theory and the Theory of Connected Experiences by John Dewey. According to Bruner's Constructivist Theory from 1960, a student can pick up any subject at any age if the education is structured properly. This idea states that when learning new content, it is efficient to move from an active to an iconic to a symbolic representation; this is true even for adult learners. Furthermore, a teacher's job should not be to rote-teach students facts but rather to aid in the learning process. This means that a skilled teacher creates lessons that assist pupils in understanding the connections between different pieces of knowledge. Both the Constructivist Theory and the utilization of learning

materials in Blended Learning are assumed to have relevance to each other as they include the strategy of teachers in facilitating the learning process as well as the progress of presentation of new learning materials to convey their lessons in the class. Furthermore, the theory is significant to the phenomenon of utilization of learning materials in blended learning wherein it is used and observed in teaching online and face-to-face environments as it is utilized by teachers to design experiences through learning materials which facilitates the student to construct their own knowledge.

Another theory that supports the argument of this study is the theory of Connected Experiences by John Dewey (1938). It emphasized the relevance of personal experience in the learning process. In each John Dewey experience, people identify their actions with the consequences of their actions. The worth of experience is found in the awareness of relationships or the continuation of occurrences. This idea emphasized that the environment provides a common experience on a daily basis when genuine issues develop from the present. Experience, offered solutions, relevant facts are observed, and theories are generated and implemented. In other words, learning is essentially an activity that stems from personal problem-solving experience. This theory was used as the basis of this study in looking at the experiences and situations that influence the learning process of a pre-service teacher in the utilization of learning materials, specifically in teaching TLE during blended learning. It emphasized the context and lived experience of using different instructional materials; how the pre-service teacher acquired the experience; and how to handle or overcome the challenging situation in assessing the TLE students, specifically in online and face-to-face classroom settings.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the stories of the pre-service teacher utilization of learning materials in teaching technology and livelihood education in blended learning. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following question:

1. What are the stories of pre-service teachers' utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE during blended learning?

Literature Review

Utilization of Learning Materials

As stated by Karen (2022) the information or content that is presented in a course is called learning materials and resources. These consist of the course's lectures, readings, textbooks, multimedia elements, and other materials. These materials can be used in both physical and virtual classrooms, but some need to be modified or entirely rewritten for the virtual environment. The best study tools are synchronized with all other course elements, including learning goals, tests, and activities. As a result, give students the fundamental knowledge they will encounter, absorb, and use in a course. They have the power to engage or demotivate students. This is particularly true for online courses, which depend on a thorough and deliberate collection of educational resources that students will access, examine, absorb, and refer to as they move through a course. These resources need to be carefully selected, organized, developed and used in a course to yield the optimum results. To maximize student learning, the planning and selection of instructional materials should address both the breadth and depth of content. The cited literature provided more background information on how learning materials might be used in teaching and what learning materials should be used in face-to-face and online learning, which served as the foundation for this study.

Moreover, Tety (2016) highlights that the success of teachers and students depends on the quality of their instruction. Second, the majority of community secondary schools in Rombo District lack basic instructional and learning resources. Thirdly, the study showed that teachers employed a variety of techniques, such as book borrowing and improvisation, to lessen the difficulties associated with locating and utilizing high-quality instructional materials.

Lebenicnik et al. (2015) noted that activities with lower participation requirements are more typical among all students. There were several distinctions between student teachers and those in other programs. Certain activities intended to satisfy the requirements of various learners were more frequently carried out by student teachers than by their classmates, but students in other study programs carried out more advanced activities on average than student teachers. According to the categorization of activities, student teachers are less likely to engage in activities that need social interaction. We discovered that personal inventiveness among the sample of student instructors is connected with a diversity of activities in just one area. The tools used by pre-service teachers in this study to teach TLE in blended learning and close the learning gap are called learning materials.

Blended learning modality

Blended learning refers to a combination of conventional face-to-face and technology-mediated instruction, and is expanding in higher instruction around the world, with a few researchers anticipating that mixed learning will end up the 'new traditional' show. In any case, mixed learning implies diverse things to distinctive individuals.

According to Masadeh (2021) however, achieving the benefits of blended learning models will not yield their fruits unless reviewing issues of training, planning, and legislation is done. Blended learning has positive and comfortable environments that will change the attitudes of students and teachers toward learning and teaching as the time and place of lessons will not be a difficulty for both. Moreover, Wu et al. (2021) demonstrated that learning styles have an impact on students' happiness with their online learning through academic emotions. Online learning satisfaction was also significantly influenced by the relationship between behavioral engagement

and learning strategies.

Tayebinik and Puteh (2013) investigated the use of technology in physical classrooms provides additional resources for the students, which is expected to boost students' confidence and competence as well as improve the quality of learning. It was also noted that one benefit of blended learning environments is their potential to provide many sources for learners.

In this study, blended learning also known as hybrid learning is a type of teaching that blends traditional place-based classroom techniques with online educational resources and chances for online engagement. It creates an attractive surrounding that alter how students and teachers experience learning and teaching since the schedule and place of classes won't be a problem for either party. Hence, there are various studies conducted on the teachers' experiences of the utilization of learning materials during blended learning. This study aimed to investigate the phenomenon of TLE pre-service teachers' utilization of learning materials in blended learning. Specifically, it intended to explore the experiences, context, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the pre-service teachers in teaching TLE students in blended learning.

Challenges of pre-service teacher in blended learning

Blended learning is defined as planned educational experiences, both within and outside of the classroom, that combine many teaching and learning modalities. Blended learning introduces and utilizes new information and communication technologies for the development of innovative learning environments to transform and improve learning.

Moreover, Jumani (2018) claimed that difficulties with internet connection due to technical issues, a lack of technological expertise, the workload of teachers, and poor audio/video connectivity during online sessions were some of the difficulties with blended learning (BL). The study has made several recommendations, including planning advanced LMS training sessions for professors and students, encouraging teachers to grade and provide feedback more effectively, and enhancing the audio/video connectivity of online sessions. Similarly, Al-Nofli (2022) claimed that the use of technology, the variety of teaching methods, and the support from colleagues were the positive and difficult parts of teaching social studies. The most problematic aspects, on the other hand, had to do with poor Internet connections, a lack of communication, challenges with implementing evaluations, a lack of instructional time, and difficulties with carrying out practical tasks. According to Rasheed et al. (2020), It is widely accepted that blended learning is a method that combines the advantages of online and face-to-face learning components.

The key issues facing educational institutions are the provision of appropriate instructional technology and adequate training support for teachers. This review emphasizes the need for additional research to address the issues of blended learning for students, teachers, and educational institutions. Dahmash1 (2020) As educational institutions around the world pushed to use blended learning efforts to ensure continuity while regulating the spread of this contagious disease, COVID-19 significantly altered the teaching process.

This study investigates the educational shifts and draws on conventional ideas about blended learning (Sharma, 2010). According to Mangubat et al. (2022), According to DepEd Order number 018 series of 2020, modular instruction is used by the Department of Education (DepEd) throughout all subject areas. Teachers are compelled by this to accept the difficulties and evolve. Accessing educational resources was frequently difficult in a discussion situation. Teachers of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) face many difficulties, including a lack of student-teacher engagement, a lack of resources, and a sense of isolation. The difficulties pre-service teachers encounter in blended learning are those related to their experiences using a variety of learning resources to present their lessons to the class.

The aforementioned literature provided more background knowledge on the difficulties faced by pre-service teachers in blended learning as it is used and regarded from various angles, which served as the study's foundation. According to this study, pre-service teachers may benefit from worthwhile learning opportunities as a result of the difficulties they face in blended learning, which will help them become more knowledgeable and adaptable to the rapidly changing educational landscape.

Coping mechanism of pre-service teacher in blended learning

Students have a lot to do at home, especially when the learning mode is blended learning. Bahian et al. (2020) revealed that the necessity to handle responsibilities at home, the adaptation of learning styles, and the lack of study space were the most frequently encountered challenges. The advantage of distant learning allows anyone to learn from any location. Since students and teachers do not have to be present physically in the classroom or present at the same time, online and distant learning methods offer the convenience of time and space. Through utilizing the Facebook page, Pedragoza (2021) stated that pupils are motivated to learn continuously when they feel their teachers are present and have access to teaching-learning tools. With the proper planning, support, and resources, students may keep learning. She further said that it is a solution for the separation of teacher and learners and that this might ease the lack of teaching learning materials, especially for TLE subject and that this could alleviate the lack of teaching-learning resources, especially for TLE subject and its specialization courses.

According to Mangubat et al. (2022), how the teachers respond to the rapid shift in instruction in the new normal has been impacted by modular classrooms. The experiences of teachers during modular instruction have been the subject of numerous research. However, there is not a specific study on the practical experiences of TLE teachers using modular instruction in high school. Rost (2019) argues that some students may be unable to properly take full advantage of online learning tools due to problems with their digital literacy.

The linked work section is used in this study as a reference and help for the phenomenon on the utilization of learning materials in blended learning. The likelihood that such actions will have detrimental outcomes was also made more evident, and it provided present researchers with a roadmap for how to thoroughly discuss the centered phenomena. According to the theories previously addressed, it is a remedy for the separation of teacher and learners, and that this could assuage the absence of teaching-learning resources, especially for TLE subject and its specialization courses. Pedragoza (2021) stated that pupils are motivated to learn continuously when they feel their teachers are present and have access to teaching-learning tools.

Teaching strategies are the coping mechanisms for handling difficult situations and effectively delivering lessons. This coincides with the information stated by Zhu et al. (2021). Several teaching methods, including presentations, peer comments, and paper analysis, were proven to be beneficial. Asynchronous learning exercises like online discussions and debates have a lower success rate. Orlich et al. (2013) emphasized the instructional demands of classroom teachers and the enhancement of teaching practices in the statement that teaching strategies are a roadmap to effective instruction. Teaching techniques aid all aspiring educators in acquiring the fundamental skills and information required to support the learning of all the children in our country.

In summary, the aforementioned reviews are essential to support the findings of the study as they reveal substantiating details about the utilization of learning materials in blended learning which is frequently used to assist pre-service teachers in teaching TLE in blended learning, particularly in blended learning where the learning environment shifts into face-to-face and online.

Methodology

Research Design

This research used a qualitative research design which is the Narrative Inquiry design. Narrative Inquiry is a method for interpreting stories that allow researchers to record the experiences of a single person or small group, presenting their lived experience or unique point of view. This is typically done mostly through interviews, which are then documented and organized into a chronological narrative (Connelly & Clandinin, 1990). Moreover, narrative inquiry revealed the perceptions and personal stories of pre-service teachers who participated in Focus Group Discussions (FGD), about the utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning. Thus, this study used a narrative inquiry research design is deemed suitable in exploring the perceptions and personal stories of pre-service teachers

Participants

This study was conducted in one of the private schools in Cagayan de Oro City in the school year 2022-2023 which involved 5 BTLE pre-service teachers. Data were gathered through an online or face to face interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) using a semi-structured interview.

The researcher made use of purposive sampling in which the participants were selected on-purpose due to their characteristics that needed in the sample following the established criteria: 1) the participants must be officially enrolled in the Teacher Education Program in the second semester of the school year 2022-2023; (2) a Teacher Education student taking Technology and Livelihood Education subject; and (3) must be 18 years old above.

Instruments

The research instrument used in this study is a semi-structured interview to gather responses from the selected participants. The researcher crafts self-made research questions for an interview.

This research instrument included questions for an interview that was helpful in the conduct of the study. The interview questions were categorized into four dimensions: Experiences, Context, Challenges, and Coping Mechanisms. Thus, the research instrument used in this study further gained in-depth data about the lived experiences of the participants of the study who utilized the learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning.

The study investigated the experiences of the utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning, especially the experiences, context, challenges, and coping strategies that pre-service teachers experienced during their online classes. The researchers-made interview questionnaire underwent content validation from the experts. The questionnaires were modified upon the suggestions and recommendations of experts.

Procedure

In the data gathering, the researcher asked permission from the Dean of the Teacher Education Program in one of the College Institutions of Cagayan De Oro City to collect responses from purposely chosen students through a consent form for legal permission.

After the consent forms were collected, the schedule of interviews was discussed with the student participants. Upon conducting the interview, the researchers distributed the informed consent to the participants of the study. After the consent was granted, the researchers introduced the study to the participants. The participants were asked if they were willing to be gathered in a private live video conference where the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was administered. This method is carefully selected to gain more concrete

responses about their experiences with the learning materials and resources in online classes. The researchers asked permission to record the said FGD for referential purposes. To generate the findings of this study, the participants were informed that any language that they are comfortable speaking is allowed. This is to ensure that the automatic of their verbal responses was filmed in this study.

Ethical Considerations

The collected responses and information from the FGD are full confidentiality and strictly observed. Every part of the participant's responses or any information given was not taken out of context and/or changed in the presentation and discussion of results and was accessible only to the researchers. After the research study, all the collected responses during the interview of the participants were used only for research purposes.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings drawn from the study. The data analysis followed by an interpretation of data which the qualitative research design used to get the actual experiences of the study's participants.

The most significant question in this research is regarding the phenomenon of utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning of the participants. This section contains the participants' stories in teaching TLE using learning materials in blended learning.

The Experiences of Pre-Service Teachers' Utilization of Learning Materials in Teaching TLE During Blended Learning

To determine the experiences of the participants, exploration of the experiences during Focus Group Discussion was administered by the researchers followed by the participant's response to the research interview and follow-up questions. In this section, pre-service teachers' experiences are fully presented in table 1.

Table 1. *Pre-service teachers Experiences of Utilization of Learning Materials in Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in Blended Learning*

<i>Main Themes</i>	<i>Sub-themes</i>	<i>General Description of the Theme</i>	<i>Significant Statements</i>
Theme 1: Challenges of Utilization of Learning Materials	Ineffective of Video Presentation	Ineffective of video presentation is an instance ineffective of utilization of learning materials in blended learning.	...for videos online, the challenge is first the internet example, you have run out of time because the videos cannot play... (Participant 2, Transcript 5, 136-137)
	Inadequate of utilization of Learning Materials	Inadequate utilization of learning materials are the lack of quality or quantity in the delivery of lessons as these instructional materials are utilized by the teachers in face-to-face and online classes.	...there is no internet connection, in face to face might the problem and challenge is the availability of the tools... (Participant 4, Transcript 7, 217-219)
	Lack of Availability of Learning Materials	Utilization of learning materials are depends of its of availability and knowledge of the teacher on how to use it as these instructional materials utilized in various teaching environment	...it is very challenging because I am a teacher that doesn't have complete technology like, laptops and Wi-Fi that needs an internet connection... (Participant 5, Transcript 6, 198-200)

Data to identify the participant's experiences of utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning were obtained from semi-structured interviews. Participants were given code-names or pseudonyms (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, and P6) for confidentiality purposes.

Theme 1: Challenges of Learning Materials (Ineffective of Video Presentation, Inadequate of Learning Materials, and Lack of Availability of Learning Materials) Challenges of Learning Materials refers to the difficulty experienced by the pre-service teachers in utilization of the learning materials during blended learning. This theme includes the Ineffectiveness of Video Presentation, Inadequate of Utilization of Learning Materials, and Lack of Availability of Learning Materials.

1.1 Ineffective of Video Presentation

Video presentation is a form of instructional materials that participants convey their lessons in blended learning. Boateng et al. (2016)

discovered how essential videos are to participants' learning goals and methodology. However, it should be emphasized that in order for instructors to use video effectively, they must put up effort and give it due consideration. Escandor (2022) stated that teachers may have issues while utilizing video-based education as instructional learning materials for pupils during the epidemic. These issues include a lack of understanding of how to use video-based lessons as a teaching tool in the classroom, the absence of teaching tools like laptops and mobile phones that can be used to access information in video-based lessons, difficulty creating video-based lessons due to poor internet connections, students' limited attention spans and disinterest in watching videos, and the time and expense required of students, especially during pandemics when not all students can afford it.

Participant 4 said, "...You already talked about it in a virtual setting, but face to face, they don't know how to use it. There is a gap..." (Participant 4, Transcript 6, Lines 176-177). The same remarks were mentioned by Participant 1 "...I saw the bad effect of giving them only videos to learn the planting, class is messed up, with some of them doing inappropriate spraying..." (Participant 1, Transcript 1, Lines 10-11). Participant 2 shared "...For the video, they are bored and sleepy, especially in crochet..." (Participant 2, Transcript 1, Lines 16-17). "...if you are doing a face-to-face demonstration, you should use online videos..." (Participant 2, Transcript 1, Lines 20). "...For the video, they can easily catch up if that video is online, while face-to-face, they are bored..." (Participant 2, Transcript 1, Lines 18-19).

Additionally, Participant 4 added that "...it so difficult because you play a video without a personal application..." (Participant 4, Transcript 5 and 4, Lines 163-164). Participant 2 also shared "...For videos online, the challenge is first the internet example, you have run out of time because the videos cannot play..." (Participant 2, Transcript 5, 136-137).

The utilization of learning materials, specifically the video presentation in blended learning, are experienced by the participants, who believe that it is ineffective, particularly in terms of motivation and application in both online and face-to-face classroom settings. The participants are able to teach using video presentations in an online setting. However, when the actual demonstration is face-to-face they cannot apply what they have learned in the video presentation presented in an online setting.

The participants acknowledge that in face-to-face the video presentation made their students lack motivation as well as in an online learning they cannot apply what are expected learnings that obtain from the video presented. This is supported by the study of Widyastuti et al. (2022) as they stated The use of learning media through video conferencing and instant messengers, as well as hybrid learning methods where students study at home and study in face-to-face classes, provide additional work for teachers because they have to focus on both. Changes in learning time make students feel less able to learn from the teacher.

The participants firmly stated that the utilization of learning materials where the video presentations are used in teaching both online and face-to-face learning are ineffective as the students are sleepy and cannot apply the lessons that should be acquired in the video presentation.

1.2 Inadequate of Utilization of Learning Materials

Inadequate utilization of learning materials are the lack of quality or quantity of the participants' using the learning materials in online and face-to-face classes. This was corroborated by Dhakal (2020), who discovered that the obstacles to using instructional materials include lack of materials, teachers' laziness, a lack of knowledge and strategies, financial constraints, a lack of appropriate materials in textbooks, a lack of time, and a lack of authority support. In addition, workshops should be conducted to educate the teachers on the challenges of using materials during teaching. The importance of use of instructional materials in teaching should not be neglected. Therefore the challenges encountered during the use of the materials, should be tackled for effective use of these materials.

Participants 2, 3, 4 and 5 mentioned that they have struggled in using the learning materials both online and face-to-face class. Participant 2 specifically shared that the learning materials that she is using cannot be play as the institution do not have an internet connection (Participant 2 Transcript 6, Lines 147 - 146) Participant 5 also shared that "...My problem is the connection I am far from the city where has a weak internet connection..." (Participant 5 Transcript 8, Lines 244 - 246) Participant 4 added that "...There is no internet connection, in face to face might the problem and challenge is the availability of the tools..." (Participant 4 Transcript 6 and 7 Lines 205 - 211)

Participant 4 shared that "...You introduced in carpentry, agri-fishery, and electronics, like this is how to do it, but you only see is videos, the difficulty here is how you make it realistic..." (Participant 4 Transcript 8, Lines 257 - 259) Participant 2 also shared that "...in embroidery or crochet, they cannot see it even if I am using some actions because it's so small..." (Participant 2 Transcript 1, Lines 19 - 20) Participant 3 stated that "...So, jam board was not applicable for elementary students..." (Participant 3 Transcript 2, Lines 56) Participant 5 expressed the challenges of using the learning materials, specifically laptop "...One of the problem of that is the application, not all laptops you can install an application that updated, since laptop has very old unit..." (Participant 5 Transcript 7, Lines 226 - 238)

Moreover, Participant 4 and 5 mentioned that they encountered challenges in finding information for their lessons and how to verify its reliability. Participant 5 stated that "...It's maybe challenges, if you want to look for another information that you can add on your learning materials..." (Participant 5 Transcript 16, Lines 552 - 553) Participant 4 added "...It's better if all of it were direct, so that you can just copy paste it once for all on your topic, that's the difficulty, its worse when your topic on TLE is broad..." (Participant 4

Transcript 16, Lines 527- 529) Participant 5 expound that "...there's a lot of information that we don't know if it is reliable or valid, we don't know if the author plagiarize their content or they are the original one since it's the one constructed..." (Participant 5 Transcript 16, Lines 517 - 519) Participant 4 also shared that "...It's very tiring to keep on searching..." (Participant 4, Transcript 16, Lines 469) "...The only things I had trouble with were creating PPTs and knowing where to find webpages..." (Participant 4 Transcript 16, Lines 511-513).

The participants expressed that the utilization of learning materials in blended learning made them struggle with its challenges. They shared that in both online and face-to-face that internet connection is one of the factors that made them struggle in using the learning materials. Participants expound the challenges of using laptops as not all laptops have HDM some of it are old units that cannot accept updated applications. This is supported by Obada et al. (2022) as he said, technical limitations like the availability of PCs, laptops, or other devices are what cause the issues. In synchronous learning, inadequate internet capabilities, such as slow or inconsistent connections, may make it impossible for students to re-join the session rooms again, stressing them out physically and mentally. Additionally, the students' varying internet connection speeds must be taken into account and the teaching materials must be made available to them asynchronously.

Furthermore, participants encountered challenges in searching for information to use for their lessons and how to verify its reliability. Wahyuningsih et al. (2021) said that the majority of teachers cited technological issues as the main barrier to creating learning tools. The participants went on to say that because the TLE course is so broad, obtaining resources to employ in the learning materials is the worst circumstance.

1.3 Lack of Availability of Learning Materials

Lack of Availability of Learning Materials in blended learning is an instance that led the participants to utilize various types of learning materials as they are teaching TLE subjects which are skill-based subjects. Tuimur and Chemwei (2015) stated that insufficient access to the necessary materials may have prevented efficient instruction and preparation. Chukwu (2016) endorsed the idea that a foundation of basic education serves as the support for the rest of the educational system. It must be made clear that one cannot discuss the use of these vital tools for teaching and learning when they are not even present.

Participant 4 was similarly stated that "...in face to face the challenge is the availability of gadgets, availability of tools and equipment, that's it..." (Participant 4 Transcript 6 and 7 Lines 205 – 211) Participant 4 also shared that "...I haven't experience traditional learning materials since my pre-service teaching..." (Participant 4 Transcript 3, Lines 96 – 97) Participant 4 added that "...I only used PowerPoint Presentation, laptop, we did not experience giving a hand-outs for students..." (Participant 4 Transcript 12, Lines 399 - 401) Participant 4 elaborate that "...High technology this time, I only used laptop..." (Participant 4 Transcript 12, Lines 410) Participant 5 shared that "...It is very challenging because I am a teacher that doesn't have complete technology like, laptops and Wi-Fi that needs an internet connection..." (Participant 5 Transcript 6, Lines 198 - 200)

The responses by the participants imply that their utilization of learning materials in blended learning made them completely experienced the challenges of teaching TLE in blended learning as the institutions' were they deployed was lack of availability of learning materials. Moreover, they preferred to utilize the learning materials according to its availability. The participants chose their own teaching styles based on the availability of the learning materials.

The present study has revealed that the utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning showed that there is a lack of availability of learning materials as well as rapid development of high technology which led the participants to shift to different learning materials. All the participant admitted that the challenges in teaching TLE in blended learning are the internet connection in both online and face-to-face classes and the availability of the learning materials, specifically the tools and materials in TLE

The findings showed that utilization of learning materials in teaching TLE in blended learning assists the participants to use different learning materials in blended learning to convey their lessons in the class. However, these video presentations are ineffective as participants believe that it has negative effects in terms of motivation and participation of the students in an online and face-to-face setting. This was supported by Lange and Costley (2020) Since there is so much information available through the use of different visual and auditory media, they said that educators shouldn't shy away from using them, but they should be mindful that poor media delivery may have negative effects on learning.

The Context of the Pre-Service Teachers' Lived Experience in the Utilization Of Learning Materials in TLE During Blended Learning

To identify the contexts of the lived experiences of the participants, the researchers' pose follow-up questions on the responses of the participants on the main formulated research interview questions. In this section, students' contexts in code-switching are presented in table 2.

Table 2. *Pre-service teachers Context of Utilization of Learning Materials in Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in Blended Learning*

<i>Main Themes</i>	<i>Suub-themes</i>	<i>General Description of the Theme</i>	<i>Significant Statement</i>
Theme2: Academic Resourcefulness	Teaching Strategies	Utilization of learning materials in blended learning has various teaching strategies that pre-service teachers constructed for them to carry out the lesson in an online and face to face setting.	...I prepared one week ahead of time, especially; in case of online or face to face, one week of time all the activities, lesson plan and all instructional materials... (Participant 5 Transcript 10, Lines 323-324)
	Flexibility	Flexibility is an ability of the pre-service teachers to handle the situation despite of the different learning materials across the blended learning to assist the learning environment	...my coping mechanism is time, another one is the flexibility, like what they have said that teacher should be flexible and always have a patience as a teacher because not all students are privilege... (Participant 5 Transcript 10, Lines 329 - 331)
	Technology Literacy	Technology Literacy is being able to read, comprehend, write and speak to understand the functions of the technology.	...no, no...It's like students now is easier and they are so literate on technology... (Participant 5, Transcript 16, Lines 500)
Theme 3: Learning Materials in Blended Learning	Online Learning Materials	Online learning materials are the instructional materials utilized by the pre-service teachers in an online setting to provide a conducive learning environment	...First is the learning materials that really useful is PowerPoint, Canva and videos... (Participant 1 Transcript 11, Lines 369 - 370)
	Face-to-Face Learning Materials	Face-to-Face learning materials are the instructional materials that assist the pre-service teachers to convey their lessons in face-to-face classroom setting.	...in face to face, is Realia especially, we teach skill-based demo, like should be hands-on... (Participant 1 Transcript 11, Lines 374 - 376)
Theme 4: Emotional Motivation	Love of Kids	Love of kids is a kind of teaching with passion where the pre-service teachers teaching style are student-centered learning.	Love of Kids ...i think the love of kids that like I want them to learn, it feels amazing as an adult... (Participant 5, Transcript 17, Lines 505-507)
	Passion for Teaching	Passion for Teaching is an attitude where the pre-service teachers are dedicated to their lessons, as a result of being an excited of the outcomes of what effort they have put in the lessons.	...there is an excitement as you have a sleepy nights to finish that presentation... (Participant 4 Transcript 18, Lines 584)
	Support System	Support system is a system where the pre-service teachers are helping each other and giving a support to overcome challenges.	...i ask for help and then willing to be critic of context, and that way I improve myself, I improve the way I teach and physically appearance... (Participant 2, Transcript 17, Lines 515-519)
	Self-Discipline (Participant 5, Transcript 18, Lines 530-534)	Self-discipline is a value that helps the pre-service teacher to defeat their weaknesses in managing their time and to act professionally.	...there is Mañana Habit that is why I said time management is not possible if you don't have a self-discipline...
	Time Management	Time management is an effective way of handling situations that pre-service teachers exercise to productively do their to-do list.	...your quizzes, performance task, time management is the key for handling difficult situation... (Participant 4, Transcript 18, Lines 539-341)

Data to identify the participants' context in utilization of learning materials in blended learning were obtained from semi-structured interviews. Participants were given code-names or pseudonyms (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5, and P6) for confidentiality purposes.

Theme 2: Academic Resourcefulness (Teaching Strategies, Flexibility, and Technology Literacy)

Academic Resourcefulness refers to the encountered strategies of utilization of learning materials that allow the participants to be flexible in any circumstances in teaching blended learning, sub-themes are Teaching Strategies, Flexibility and Technology Literacy.

2.1 Teaching Strategies

Teaching strategies are the coping mechanism of the participants in handling difficult situations to deliver the lessons in an effective way. Zhu et al. (2021) claimed that a few teaching techniques, such as presentations, peer feedback, and paper analysis, were shown to be beneficial. Asynchronous learning exercises like online discussions and debates have a lower success rate. The fact that BL promoted community building, improved contacts and interactivities, and gave them access to quick feedback was appreciated by the students. F2F and online sessions, however, may present other difficulties. Students would also prefer for technology applications in BL to be streamlined and simplified, and maybe more critically, with enough training and quick technical assistance.

Moreover, Lapitan et al. (2021) noted that difficulties included instructor familiarity with easily available internet-based teaching tools, like video conferencing software, and internet connection stability. In order to keep students' interest and engagement levels high throughout online classes, instructors must develop ways to enhance their interactions with them.

As shared by participants 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 "...The strategy of it is, I will tell them that I will post it in the Google Classroom, so that they can re-watch it, and they know what the procedure in the video..." (Participant 4 Transcript, Lines 333 -336) Participant 4 added "...it should be realistic on students by presenting facts, and videos, and picture..." (Participant 4 Transcript 9, Lines 305 - 313) "...I think it is just a matter of how you introduce the tool that you expect them to know about already..." (Participant 4 Transcript 6 and 7, Lines 206 - 209) P3 also shared that "...I provide step-by-step videos for them to identify the proper procedure of the particular activity..." (Participant 3 Transcript 2, Lines 41 - 43) Participant 4 added "...You should download it already..." (Participant 4 Transcript 10, Lines 322)

Additionally, Participant 1 and 2 shared that when presenting video presentation, it should have short duration to avoid boredom. Participant 2 stated that "...I use a short video duration to avoid boredom..." (Participant 2 Transcript 2, Lines 30) Participant 1 added "...As much as possible 2-3 minutes..." (Participant 1 Transcript 1, Lines 31) Participant 3 specifically shared that "...When discussing online, you should not just be talking, as my mentor said, she taught me that a small duration of discussion..." (P3, Transcribe19, Lines)540-544) Participant 4 shared the same strategy "...There are times that I'll put pictures of tools since it is not good that you only put words..." (Participant 4 Transcript 2, Lines 67-71) Participant 3 specifically said that "...It should not be just one activity or breakout room in online, but prepare 2 or 3 to avoid the boring situation..."(Participant 3 Transcript 2, Lines 39 - 41) Participant 2 mentioned that "...I choose a specific video that they can obtain..." (Participant 2 Transcript 1, Lines 24-25)"...if you are doing a face-to-face demonstration, you should use online videos..." (Participant 2, Transcript 1, Lines 20) Participant 2 added "...I need to reserve a flash drive to be fast for it to save and I can play it..." (Participant 2 Transcript 6, Lines 175 -176).

The participants primarily stated in their responses that when it comes to utilization of learning materials in both online and face-to-face classes, they constructed strategies to avoid technical issues in using the instructional materials. They shared that when presenting a video presentation, it should have a short duration to avoid boredom. As stated by Kösterelioğlu (2016) The length, objectives, and quantity of the movies must all be appropriate. This underlines that videos should not take up the entire class period and should have adequate sound and image quality. Additionally, PowerPoint presentations need to be visually appealing since they suggest that including memes, activities, games, breakout rooms, photos, and Realia in blended learning lessons will help students pay attention.

Moreover, the participants expound on the strategy, specifically the video presentation should be downloaded including the preparation of flash drive to save the files when the connection is poor. This means that these situations push them to construct strategies to make use of the instructional materials in blended learning. Sarbeni et al. (2022) mentioned that lecturers might use Zoom Video Conference as a useful substitute medium for recorded course presentations and assignments.

2.2 Flexibility

Flexibility is an ability of the participants to handle the situations in utilization of learning materials in both online and face-to-face settings which support them to build a conducive learning environment. This is supported by Corpus et al. (2022) affirmed that "Teachers are Very Flexible" in putting the five facets of flexibility into practice: time, content, entry requirements, instructional approach and resources, delivery, and logistics.

Similar remarks from participants 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 stated that "...teachers should be flexible to manage the situations in the classroom..." Participant 5 shared that "...My coping mechanism is time, another one is the flexibility, like what they have said that teacher should be flexible and always have a patience as a teacher because not all students are privilege..." (Participant 5 Transcript 10, Lines 329 - 331) Participant 3 added "...Yes, as what you have observed in our answers earlier, there is positive and negative, so as a Pre-service teacher intern here, we need to be flexible at all times..." (Participant 3 Transcript 14, Lines 465 - 467) Participant 1 shared that

“...some students that is not around and the teachers will distribute a book to the student usually those activities that they needed to answer...” (Participant 1 Transcript 9, Lines 281 - 283)

The participants shared that teachers should be flexible and know how to adapt to the situation as not all the students are privileged to cope up with the learning materials that they utilized. They also shared that being flexible is one of the factors that teachers should possess to overcome the challenges in the classroom. As stated by Lübke et al. (2021) Flexibility had both direct and indirect benefits on attitudes, self-efficacy, and intentions and behavior. This understanding of flexibility could be used to better prepare student teachers for their work in schools. This indicates that instructors, who are more adaptable in terms of their job requirements, anticipate inclusive education having a greater positive impact on students' academic progress.

2.3 Technology Literacy

In utilization of learning materials in blended learning, technology literacy is one of the factors that students possess which helps the participants to make it easier in teaching and utilizing the learning materials in the classroom. Shopova (2014) said that increasing students' digital literacy and ICT usage abilities is a necessary precondition for good performance and higher learning outcomes.

Participant 4 and 5 stated that students are more advance and literate in technology. Participant 5 shared that “...No, no...It's like students now is easier and they are so literate on technology...” (Participant 5, Transcript18, Lines 554-557) Participant 4 also shared “...and they are not alien on what you will teach since they have read it already, they have advance reading...” (Participant 4, Transcript19, Lines561-563). The participants shared that students are easy to teach as they are more advanced and literate in utilizing the learning materials in an online setting. This means that the occurrence of utilization of learning materials is influenced by the students' literacy in the technology. This is supported by Santoso and Lestari (2019) Students that are more technologically literate will benefit from having access to more references. Students employ technical improvements to locate a variety of learning resources, add their own ideas, and apply technological advancements to regular learning activities like creating presentations and simplifying learning media.

Theme 3: Learning Materials in Blended Learning(Online Learning Materials and Face-to-Face Learning Materials)

Learning Materials in Blended learning are the materials utilized to assist in attainment of the learning target. This theme includes the Online Learning Materials and Face-to-Face Learning Materials.

3.1 Online Learning Materials

Online learning materials is a collection of materials that participants used in teaching TLE to help achieve the learning objectives. There are three types of learning materials used by the participants during their teaching TLE in online learning such as Visual, Audio-visual and Electronic interactive. These learning materials utilized the participants during teaching TLE in blended learning. Edu (2022) mentioned that by using a few articles or materials to support their verbal descriptions, teachers might make their classes really engaging and significant for the pupils. It has been shown that using a wide range of resources helps students understand concepts better and makes studying genuinely interesting. Instructional material or teaching aids are other names for teaching-learning materials.

Participants 1 and 4 shared their utilization of online learning materials. Specifically, Audio-visual and Electronic Interactive instructional materials that used in teaching TLE in an online learning. Participant 1 stated that “...first is the learning materials that really useful is PowerPoint, Canva and videos...” (Participant 1 Transcript 11, Lines 369 - 370) Participant 4 added “...I use a Canva or PowerPoint presentation...” (Participant 1 Transcript 11, Lines 369 - 370) Participant 3 added “...I use YouTube and Google Slide...” (Participant 3 Transcript 11, Lines 371 and 373) “I used Google meet...” (Participant 3 Transcript 2, Lines 48) Participant 4 also shared “...I used Padlet...” (Participant 4 Transcript 4, Lines 117) “..I use Jam board...” (Participant 4 Transcript 4, Line 121) Participant 1 state that “...I utilized these quizzes and Jam board...” (Participant 1 Transcript 2, Lines 55) Participant 5 expound it more by sharing the utilized learning materials during her teaching “...There's a lot of social websites such as Kahoot...” (Participant 5 Transcript 3, Lines 105) “...Google Classrooms...” (Participant 5 Transcript 4, Lines 122 - 123) “...The platform now is Zoom, Quizlet, and Google Meet...” (Participant 5 Transcript 4, Lines 122 - 123) Participant 2 also shared that ‘...The second one is the gadget, my phone...” (Participant 2 Transcript 6, Lines 180)

As expressed by the participants, they utilized different teaching-learning materials in online learning such as Visual, Audio-visual and Electronic. This is supported by Edu (2022) noted that teachers frequently employ various teaching strategies and technologies to engage students and deliver high-quality instruction. Teachers can use teaching-learning materials, or TLMs, to help students learn more efficiently.

Furthermore, participants shared that the learning materials that were useful are the PowerPoint Presentation, Canva and Videos as the institution has a high technology which led the participants to use online learning materials. The participants also utilized these materials; YouTube, Google Slide, Google Meet, Padlet, Jam board, Quizzes, Kahoot, Google Classroom, and Zoom, Quizlet to provide an effective learning environment. Thus, teaching-learning materials that they have used assist their teaching in blended learning as they utilized it to create an interactive learning environment. This is supported by Alenezi (2020) finding that student performance and teaching practices were more effective when e-learning resources and tools were used more frequently in educational settings.

3.2 Face-to-Face Learning Materials

The face-to-face learning materials are the instructional learning materials used by the participants in order to aid the conducive learning environment. There are four types of learning materials such as Print, Visual, Audio-visual and Electronic Interactive. These learning materials utilized the participants during teaching TLE in face-to-face classes. Frimpong (2021) stated that teachers should come up with creative strategies to build TLMs in their community. Additionally, they ought to support and encourage kids' active engagement with TLMs since this is a sure-fire way to ensure learning.

Participant 1 and 2 shared their utilization of visual type of learning materials "...In face to face, is Realia especially, we teach skill-based demo, like should be hands-on..." (Participant 1, Transcript 19, Lines 568-570) "...I am using specific learning styles such as Realia..." (Participant 2 Transcript 1, Lines 18 - 19) Participant 4 shared her utilization of learning materials. Specifically, electronic interactive "...I use a Canva or PowerPoint presentation..." (Participant 4 Transcript 3, Lines 94 - 95) Participant 5 mentioned that she used print types of learning materials "...Maybe in my case, I gave hand-outs, it is soft copy like I prepared Cartolina..." (Participant 5 Transcript 12, Lines 402 - 403) "... You are doing a face-to-face demonstration, you should use online video..." (Participant 2, Transcript, Lines).

The study revealed that participants utilized Print, Visual, Visual-Audio and Electronic Interactive types of teaching-learning materials (TLM). They expressed that in teaching TLE should utilized visual, electronic Interactive and print teaching-learning materials as TLE are skill-based courses. They expound that in face-to-face, teaching-learning materials such as audio-visual can be used to assist the presentation. Adalikwuand Iorkpilgh (2013) claimed that the usage of instructional resources often enhanced students' conceptual understanding and produced impressive academic results.

Theme 4: Emotional Motivation (Love of Kids, Excitement, Support System, Self-Discipline, and Time Management)

Emotional Motivation refers to the encountered emotions of utilization of learning materials that led the participants to be motivated in any situation Sub-themes are Love of Kids, Excitement, Support System, Self-discipline and Time Management.

4.1 Love of Kids

Love of kids is a passion of the participants in teaching TLE in blended learning which made them overcome or handled the difficulty or challenges in utilization of learning materials. This is supported by Dennis (2012) Teachers agreed that providing pre-service teachers with training in caring, forming connections, and ethics would probably have a transformative impact on education even though they had no formal instruction in how to love.

Participant 5 and 3 mentioned that "...I think the love of kids that like I want them to learn, it feels amazing as an adult..." (Participant 20, Transcript 20, Lines 576-576) "...Yes, it is under of ""Teaching is a Profession""..." (Participant 3 Transcript 19, Lines 624) The participants expressed that in coping up with the challenges of utilization of learning materials was the love of kids as it is under the "Teaching is a Profession". It was also stated that it feels amazing as an adult to teach the students. This is supported by Da Luz (2015) stated that interaction is crucial to the teacher-student relationship and that both teachers and students value a supportive and caring relationship between them. Students are motivated to become more interested learners by feeling that their teachers care about them and are there for them. A kind instructor will support both pupils and themselves through challenges.

4.2 Passion for Teaching

Passion for teaching is an attitude that the participants feel every time they utilize the learning materials especially, in terms of making the presentation for their students. Hartman et al. (2019) The importance of professional development and training, self-motivation, and excitement about how technology can enhance learning, along with worries about the lack of infrastructure and support for integrating technology, and about students' ability to use the tools for higher ordered thinking, surfaced, according to the statement.

Participants 2 and 4 expressed that they felt an excitement in making the presentation for the student despite the challenges that they have encountered. Participant 2 shared "...I feel exciting and challenging, especially when there are many unexpected challenges..." (Participant 2, Transcript, Lines) Participant 4 added that "...here is an excitement as you have a sleepy night to finish that presentation..." (Participant 2, Transcript 21, 579-582). Participant 4 added "...I am excited to show them the pictures that I saved as it makes them hungry..." (Participant 4, Transcript, Lines 5-884-884).

Participants shared that using the learning materials made them feel excitement despite the challenges. In utilization of learning materials, they felt excitement as they experienced sleepless nights to make the presentation as well as the electronic interactive types of learning materials that they enhance to transform it into an effective presentation. Wright (2011) showed that educators thought it was beneficial to use technology in the classroom and that they were at ease and excited about doing so. In addition, Yalçin et al. (2017) claimed that educational programs involve teaching practice using real-world material. It is a strategy designed to spark curiosity and excitement in the home environment and the classroom setting that supports the continuity of the program.

4.3 Support System

Support System is an instance when an individual needs a support in the challenges in different circumstances. An individual usually

asking for help to as most of the resources are not available or challenges should be done with group of people. Simpson (2010) reported that the variables most influencing their decision to stay in teaching and the effectiveness of their instruction are mentoring and collaboration with colleagues.

Participant 2 stated that "...ask for help and then willing to be critic of context, and that way I improve myself, I improve the way I teach and physically appearance..." (Participant 2, Transcript, Lines,) same remarks with participant 4 "...I ask for help..." (Participant 4 Transcript 11, Lines 355) "...Yes, give and take, if you feel she can't do it, just help her and if you feel the same, ask for help..." (Participant 4, Transcript 20, Lines 585-585) Participant 5 added "...all I want to say is never be afraid to ask for help..." (Participant 5 Transcript 22, Lines 701 - 702) Participant 5 mentioned that "...One of my coping mechanism is STs' is One of Us..." (Participant 5 Transcript 10, Lines 345 - 346) "...like our quotes is, "Same major, Have One Head", like that one head is a source of energy..." (Participant 5 Transcript 11, Lines 359 - 361) "...your same majors will help you, you help each other, as you have the same major, and you should have the same brain..." (Participant 5 Transcript 11, Lines 359 - 361)

The participants believed that asking for help with the same course on the utilization of the learning materials in the class assists them in teaching TLE in blended learning. They shared that their coping mechanism of the challenges in using learning materials are each of them as they are helping each other morally and physically. This is supported by Reitman (2019) claiming that their continued employment in the field was largely due to this early assistance. Beginning on the first day of instruction, support must be given, and it must continue until the instructor can show that he or she has attained the impact level in every area.

4.4 Self-discipline

Self-discipline is an ability to deal with emotions and handle weaknesses as this ability is to pursue the right thing despite the temptations to abandon it. According to Barni et al. (2019), teachers' personal values have been found to be significant predictors of their level of self-efficacy. Particularly, conservation was strongly correlated with teachers' self-efficacy, regardless of whether they were driven by regulated or autonomous goals at work.

Participant 5 shared that "...Time management is not that possible but if you have self-discipline, it's all set..." (Participant 5 Transcript 22, Lines 676 - 677) "...there is Mañana Habit that is why I said time management is not possible if you don't have a self-discipline..." (Participant 5 Transcript 22, Lines 692 - 693) "...I'm not sure but actually, based on my observation to my co-ST, is discipline..." (Participant 5, Transcript 21, Lines 521-521).

Due to the challenges that pre-service teachers encountered, the responses indicated that self-discipline should be practiced over time management as it is one of the participants' observations to each other. Pre-service teachers are found to have a Mañana Habit but they claimed that it would not be a habit if the self-discipline possessed of a pre-service teacher. This is supported by Setyowati (2019) stating that the discipline in planning, implementing, and evaluating the learning process directly can be formed in carrying out the duties and responsibilities of the teacher as a professional educator. Practically, the established teacher discipline facilitates teachers' ability to meet the requirements of all teacher performance competencies, including educational, personal, social, and professional competence.

4.5 Time Management

Time management is an ability to make use of the time effectively and productively. It makes an individual able to handle the difficulty of a schedule in everyday challenges. This was supported by Lualhati (2019) noted that in order to manage their time, the faculty members practiced scheduling, goal-setting, task prioritization, managing paperwork, and managing interruptions; nonetheless, a hurdle they encountered was dealing with the volume of paperwork and reports.

As stated by Participant 5 "...there is no other thing that is better that managing your time..." (Participant 5 Transcript 22, Lines 676 - 677) same remarks with Participant 4 "...You know, all I can say is 'Time Management'..." (Participant (Participant 4 Transcript 20, Lines 640) Participant 5 shared that "...Time management, but sometimes it's not..." (Participant 5 Transcript 20, Lines 641) Participant 4 also shared "...So, My mentor gave a unit plan advance, so I make a learning plan a head of time..." (Participant 4, Transcript 22, Lines 601-601) "...Your quizzes, performance task, time management is the key for handling difficult situation..." (Participant 4, Transcript 22, Lines 605-606)

The pre-service responses were supported by Olivo (2021) who asserted that teachers' time management techniques included everything from identifying critical chores for the day to planning ahead of time to staying late at home to complete duties. Delegating tasks was shown to be one of their least effective time management techniques.

Overall, the findings showed that the participants' utilization of learning materials mainly pushes them to strategize and be flexible towards the situation. This means that they constructed strategies to avoid technical issues in using the instructional materials.

It revealed that participants utilized learning materials in blended learning such as print, visual, audio-visual and electronic interactive. This means that teaching-learning materials that they have used assist their teaching in blended learning as they utilized it to create an interactive learning environment and in face-to-face, teaching-learning materials such as audio-visual can be used to assist the presentation

Conclusions

The findings of this study showed that the lived experiences and the context of the pre-service teachers mainly revolve around the challenges and coping strategies of using learning materials to assist in teaching TLE in blended learning.

It is confirmed that the effective implementation of blended learning relies on academic resourcefulness, a combination of online and face-to-face learning materials, and emotional motivation among teachers. By recognizing and addressing these aspects, educators can enhance the overall learning experience and support the teaching of TLE subjects in a blended learning environment.

Also, the results confirmed Bruner's Constructivist Theory, which suggests that with proper structure and guidance, even very young learners can grasp any subject. This finding is aligned with John Dewey's theory of connectedness (1938), which posits that a student's learning experiences, decisions, and behavior are interconnected, demonstrating continuity of experience in the context of this study.

Self-related perceptions of the self should be enhanced through the school's environment and learning activities. Despite that, it can be assumed that higher self-concept will not predict academic performance; either way, students' academic performance does not reflect on their self-concept. Likewise, it should be noted that the respondents were still in the process of searching for their unique identities. Further, students need extensive educational learning experience from the school and their environment to harness their skills and develop their self-efficacy.

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